

THE DYNAMICS OF THE FORMATION AND DEVELOPMENT OF INTERNATIONAL HIGHER EDUCATION INSTITUTIONS IN THE MODERN EDUCATIONAL POLICY OF UZBEKISTAN (ON THE EXAMPLE OF ANDIJAN REGION)

Salimboyeva Farzona Khojiakbar qizi

Master's student, Andizhan State University

Tel: +998932551282

ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0009-0002-3333-1183>

E-mail: iskandarolimov815@gmail.com

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19394573>

Abstract: This article provides a historical and scientific analysis of the establishment of international higher education institutions in the Andijan region, evaluating their developmental trajectory and broader historical significance.

Keywords: Higher education institution, private institution, university, direction, specialization, student.

Introduction

Nowadays, higher education institutions operating in different regions of the world, with a wide range of specializations, have become an important component of the global education system. These institutions do not use a single pedagogical approach, but introduce different methodologies in accordance with their goals and objectives. As a result, competition between them is also increasing along with the increasing number of educational entities. In particular, some higher education institutions have acquired international status and provide educational services through their branches in many countries of the world. The process of global educational integration has not bypassed Uzbekistan. In recent years, as a result of the entry of international higher education institutions into the country, a competitive environment has been formed in the education market, which is giving impetus to improving the quality of education and management efficiency in local higher education institutions. In particular, a number of international universities and institutes have begun operating in the Andijan region. This, on the one hand, expands the opportunities for young people to obtain education that meets international standards without long-distance travel, and on the other hand, serves as a methodological and organizational model for local higher education institutions, strengthening healthy competition.

Results

The concept of higher education is generally considered to be a broad one, and the Encyclopædia Britannica defines the term as follows: "Higher education is education beyond secondary school, especially at a college or university. Previously reserved primarily for religious leaders, this education now leads to a higher social status in the modern economy. It is also where the greatest restrictions on admission occur. Worldwide, at the beginning of the 21st century, fewer than a fifth of 18-24 year-olds had attended some form of higher education, and in the least developed countries, less than 5 percent had. Recent trends include the rapid growth of private institutions, closer links to the market, and institutional stratification [1]."

By 2023, the number of universities operating in Uzbekistan will reach 213, of which 30 are foreign [2]. In 2002, the first international university in Uzbekistan, the University of

Westminster, was established in Tashkent [3. P. 354]. The establishment of this university was a beginning for Uzbekistan.

On January 15, 2019, Shuhratbek Abdurakhmonov, the governor of Andijan region, signed a memorandum with Sharda University in New Delhi, India, to open the first international university in Andijan. According to this memorandum, the university agreed to open its branch in the region and invest \$ 100 million [4]. It is noteworthy that Sharda University is not only the first private international university in Andijan, but also in Uzbekistan [5].

On April 10, 2019, the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev adopted the Resolution No. PQ-4278 “On the establishment of Sharda University in Uzbekistan”. This year, the university was supposed to train specialists in electrical engineering, information technologies and cybersecurity, computer systems maintenance, electronics, communication engineering, business management and other areas [6].

On October 19, 2019, the opening ceremony of Sharda University was held. The event was attended by the Governor of Andijan region of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shukhrat Abdurakhmanov and the Chief Minister of Gujarat state of the Republic of India, Mr. Vijay Rupani [7].

Since this event, Sharda University has been actively operating in Andijan. The university has introduced modern teaching methods, taking on the task of complying with the requirements of the education system in Uzbekistan.

On April 14, 2021, the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan adopted a resolution on the establishment of the Andijan branch of the Warsaw University of Management “Collegium Numanum”, which entered into force on that day [8]. This is the second international O.T.M organization opened in the Andijan region. Educational processes at this university are conducted in English, Russian and Uzbek languages [9].

Conclusion

Today, the Republic of Uzbekistan is recognized worldwide in various fields and is recognized on the global stage for its economic, social and scientific potential. In particular, the achievements in the field of higher education are significant, and important steps are being taken to adapt the country's education system to world standards and introduce modern pedagogical and scientific experiences. In order to study international educational experience and expand the educational opportunities of the local younger generation, the Republic of Uzbekistan supports the opening of branches of a number of foreign higher educational institutions. This practice not only serves to train students as highly qualified and competitive specialists, but also to improve the quality of education in the country and integrate modern scientific approaches.

These two higher educational institutions established in the city of Andijan are also intended to serve the implementation of the above-mentioned goals, to train students according to international standards, and to improve their professional and academic competencies. At the same time, the branches provide Uzbek youth with the opportunity to get acquainted with foreign educational programs, learn innovative pedagogical methods, and take advantage of international scientific and educational cooperation. This will not only improve the quality of the local education system, but also significantly contribute to the scientific and social development of the country.

Adabiyotlar, References, Литературы:

1. Higher education // Encyclopaedia Britannica. — URL: <https://www.britannica.com/topic/higher-education>
2. The number of higher education institutions in Uzbekistan and students studying in them has been announced, Kun.uz, February 14, 2024. URL: <https://kun.uz/news/2024/02/14/ozbekistondagi-otm-va-ularda-talim-oliyed-talabalar-soni-malum-qilindi>
3. Salimboeva F. (2025). The first international university in Central Asia and its activities. Society and Innovation, 6 (4/S), 353–356. <https://doi.org/10.47689/2181-1415-vol6-iss4/S-pp353-356>
4. A branch of Sharda University will be established in Andijan // XS.uz. – 2019. – January 15. – URL: <https://web.archive.org/web/20200220134315/http://xs.uz/uz/post/andizhonda-sharda-universitetining-filiali-tashkil-etiladi>
5. About Sharda University Uzbekistan // shardauniversity.uz. – URL: <https://www.shardauniversity.uz/about-us>
6. Foreign university opens in Andijan // NORMA.UZ. – 2019. – April 12. – URL: <https://www.norma.uz/oz/qonunchilikda-yangi-andijonda-horijiy-universitet-ochiladi>
7. Inauguration ceremony of Sharda University Campus in Uzbekistan on 19th October 2019 // Sharda University. – 2019. – October 19. – URL: https://www.sharda.ac.in/connect/news-details/inauguration-ceremony-of-sharda-university-campus-on-19th-october-2019?utm_source
8. Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated 14.04.2021 No. 211 “On the establishment of the Andijan branch of the Warsaw University of Management Collegium Humanum” // Buxgalter.uz. – URL: https://iibb.uz/uz/menu/ozbekiston-respublikasi-vazirlar-mahkamasining-qarorlari?utm_source
9. A branch of the Warsaw University of Management was opened in Andijan // Yuz.uz. – 2021. – 16Apr. – URL: https://yuz.uz/en/news/a-branch-of-the-warsaw-university-of-management-was-opened-in-andijan?utm_source